

The epistemological philosophy of history and strategic thought of Ibn Khaldūn (d. 1406) and Arnold Toynbee (d. 1975).

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ABSTRACT: Some ascribe the founding of historical philosophy to the Italian philosopher Vico (1668–1744), while others credit the French philosopher Montesquieu (1689–1755). In fact, Ibn Khaldūn (1332–1406), a Muslim historian, was the first to recognize that history, like any other science, required inquiry. Followed by Arnold Toynbee (d. 1975), both view history as being the science of circumstances and events with profound causes. As a result, it is an old, original part of wisdom that deserves to be considered one of its sciences. Criticism, observation, comparison, and examination were all part of Ibn Khaldūn's and Toynbee's techniques. They employed scientific criticism to examine historical stories, their sources, and historians' methodology, studying and comparing numerous versions in order to eliminate falsifications and exaggerations and arrive at an objective understanding of what had truly transpired. Because they were written to please a king or serve the goals of a sect, many narratives contained lies. For their own purposes, the newsmakers and storytellers purposefully cheated and misrepresented the information. In order to be capable of effective criticism and clarification, Ibn Khaldūn and Arnold Toynbee urged historians to become educated, accurate in observation, and proficient in comparing text with subtext. This is the intention of this article.

Key words: Ibn Khaldūn, Arnold Toynbee, al-Muqadimah, Study of History, Qur'ān, 'Aṣabiyya, historical philosophy, civilizations.

Conclusion

History is a study of human development in its entire political, social, economic, intellectual, and spiritual aspects, whatever the features, phenomena, and trends of this development. The term "history" means a group of events that have appeared in the life of humanity. History is a branch of human knowledge that aims to collect, verify, record, and interpret information about the past, as it records past events in their sequence and pursues but does not stop at recording these events. Rather, by highlighting the interconnectedness of these events, explaining the causal relationship between them, tries to explain the development that occurred in the lives of different nations, societies, and civilizations, explaining how this development occurred and why it occurred.

An overview of the introduction to history is essential in order to analyze how it is used to raise or break the spirits of nations. Then, we will look into some of the views of selected

thinkers, precisely Ibn Khaldūn (d. 808/1406) and Arnold Toynbee (d. 1975).¹ We will discuss Ibn Khaldūn's perceptions of the role of 'Aṣabiyya, or solidarity, in the establishment of states, and we will study the impact of challenges on the Renaissance, the effect of ideas on the occurrence of progress, and the impact of the conflict on resources on the establishment of states. We will also discuss some of the laws related to the revival of the Qur'ān. In addition to the most important works of thinkers, each of these talks about the subject from his perspective, and identifies the factors that lead to the revival or backwardness of any nation, so taking different opinions on the issue and learning from each individual and implementing them on the ground will lead to the renaissance of society.

The Renaissance project tries to shed light on the rules that propel nations and communities to rise or fall. The philosophy of history is concerned with the issue of philosophy of history and how to approach historical events and years with knowledge, thoughtfulness, and insight in order to get a better understanding of the methods, means, and consequences of change. It is important to consider the perspectives of certain philosophers and historians on the events and motives that shape history. Other than books of pure human growth that have been tired by the numerous repetitions, there is an instructional or developmental purpose to talking about a particular issue, i.e., strategic thinking in comprehending history.

And at this historical crossroads, when the echo of global transformations has become deafening, dreams have vanished, and the Arab nation emerges from beneath the long historical ruins, bare-chested in the face of enormous challenges and difficulties, nations striving for immunity, strength, and dominance. Although the scene appears bleak at first glance, anyone who understands the movement of history understands that every revival is preceded by a long night, and just as all nations of the world set off, our nation is launched today. It is undeniably capable of attaining the reasons for strength and immunity, even after a while. These are the hopes and goals that inspired the Renaissance effort. To propose solutions, recognize problems, and inspire optimism.

The importance of studying history:

An introduction to the merits of the science of history, the investigation of its doctrines, and the knowledge of what is presented to historians as fallacies, mentioning some of their causes. According to Ibn Khaldūn's *al-Muqaddimah*:

History is a valuable doctrine of numerous benefits and honorable purpose; it informs us about bygone nations in the context of their habits, prophets in the context of their lives, and kings in the context of their states and politics, so that those who seek the guidance of the past in either worldly or religious matters may have that advantage. 2

It takes many disadvantages, a broad range of knowledge, sound judgment, and a strong resolve to come to the truth while avoiding wrongdoing and fallacies. If news is handed along, it doesn't obey the laws of habit, politics, the nature of construction, and human

¹ A.J. Toynbee (1936). *A Study of History* London: Oxford University Press.

² Ibn Khaldūn, Abu Zaid 'Abd al-Raḥmān ibn Muḥammad (d. 808/1406). *Muqaddima Ibn Khaldūn* ed. Abu 'Abdullah al-Sa'īd, Beirut: Dar Iḥyā' al-Turāth al-'Arabī, 2015, p. 4.

community circumstances, and the person who isn't there isn't measured by the person who is and the person who isn't there, so it may not believe in it. Historians, commentators, and transmission scholars have frequently fallen into fallacies in the stories and facts because they relied solely on the transmission of weak or massive amounts of information. They did not expose it to its origins, measure it with its likeness, probe it according to the standard of wisdom, or act judiciously and with insight on the news. Especially when it comes to calculating the quantities of finances and troops in the tales, as there is a suspicion of exaggeration and the spread of gossip, they must be restored to the principles and presented according to the standards.

Concerned individuals wonder about the value of studying history. Isn't there the Qur'ān that was revealed by Almighty God, and the Sunnah of His Messenger, and in them what is sufficient for studying history? In order to address this concern, it is important to take into consideration a very important fact.³ The knowledge of the Book of Allah, the Qur'an, is divided into two branches of knowledge.⁴ The first is the knowledge of the Qur'an, and the second is the knowledge that was referred to by the Qur'ān.⁵ The knowledge of the Book of Allah, the Qur'an, and the traditions of the prophets is the kind of knowledge that helps you understand how to do things like worship and what not to do. However, the Qur'an referred to another knowledge. The Qur'ānic verse reads:

Many similar ways (and mishaps of life) were faced by nations (believers and disbelievers) that have passed away before you (as you have faced in the battle of Uhud), so travel through the earth, and see what was the end of those who disbelieved (in the Oneness of Allah, and disobeyed Him and His Messengers). Q. 2: 137.

The above verse explains the knowledge that is required of the place, the search, and the discovery of its rules and regulations by humans, in order to look into the conditions of the nations. This is the knowledge that we refer to and intend to discuss. In the following Qur'ānic verses of the same chapter, read:

138. This (the Qur'ān) is a plain statement for mankind, a guidance and instruction to those who are al-Muttaqun (the pious - see V.2:2).139. So do not become weak (against your enemy), nor be sad, and you will be superior (in victory) if you are indeed (true) believers. 140. If a wound (and killing) has touched you, be sure a similar wound (and killing) has touched the others. And so are the days (good and not so good), We give to men by turns, that Allah may test those who believe, and that He may take martyrs from among you. And Allah likes not the Zalimun (polytheists and wrongdoers). 141. And that Allah may test (or purify) the believers (from sins) and destroy the disbelievers. Q. 2: 138-141.

³ 'Alī Muḥammad Muḥammad Ṣallābī, (2005). *The Noble Life of the Prophet* Riyadh: Darussalam, vol. 1, pp. 15-16.

⁴ Ghazzālī (2010). *Al-Ghazzālī : The Message From On High* tr. Margaret Smith, Kuala Lumpur: Islamic Book Trust, pp. 24-34.

⁵ Anis Ahmad (1982). "Reorientation of Islamic History: Some Methodological Issues", in *Islam: Source and Purpose of Knowledge* Islamization of knowledge series Herndon: International Institute of Islamic Thought (IIIT), vol. 5, pp. 285-312.

In the above verse, Q. 2: 137, the Qur'án refers to "traveling through the earth." It is an indication of the path to discovering the laws, and the Qur'án shows us a broad scope to discover human phenomena and draw lessons. Knowing these laws makes people firm in dealing with the existing situations. The context of the verses indicates that they were used in the field of conflict. There are believers who get sore and revolve around them. The Holy Qur'an, after commanding them to walk on earth, tells them that pain is reciprocal between all human beings and that days between people are different. In another chapter of the Qur'án, it is advocated that the task of the believer is to search for these verses spread across the horizons in order to discover the realities of existence.

We will show them Our Signs in the universe and in their own selves until it becomes manifest to them that this (the Qur'án) is the truth. Is it not sufficient in regard to your Lord that He is a Witness over all things? Q. 41: 53

Therefore, in another verse, it says:

It is only those who have knowledge among His slaves that fear Allah. Verily, Allah is All-Mighty, Oft-Forgiving. Q. 35: 28.

Scholars are fearful because they are aware of the traditions and behaviors that are presented on the horizon, as well as because they see the realities of the universe as it moves and is consistent with what God has indicated.⁶ Therefore, the study of history and research in cosmic traditions is a divine demand, and it is a rational requirement.⁷ History is at the heart of the human experience. Those who are ignorant of historical knowledge, who do not understand and appreciate the importance of history, are bound to fail. When people make mistakes, they should avoid and learn from them, and they should be more ambitious in their search for success.⁸

The *ummah*, or community as a whole, must have scholars in charge of guiding others to God's laws in His creation, just as they did in other sciences and arts to which the Qur'an guided in general, and among them the scholars in detail, pursuant to His guidance, such as monotheism, origins, and jurisprudence. Knowledge of God Almighty is one of the most significant and valuable sciences. The Qur'an as a whole is cited several times, and it has taught Muslims how it views the world. It instructed people to travel the globe in search of clarity and understanding.⁹

⁶ M. A. Muqtader Khan (1999). "Reason and Individual Reasoning", *American Journal of Islamic Social Sciences*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. v-xi.

⁷ Ahmed Hasan Dani (1982). "The Typology of Muslim Historiography from the Perspective of the Islamic Philosophy of History", in *Islam: Source and Purpose of Knowledge*, Islamization of Knowledge series, vol. 5, pp. 313-324.

⁸ See the work of Louay M. Safi (2021). *Islam and the Trajectory of Globalization: Rational Idealism and the Structure of World History* New York: Routledge.

⁹ Khaled Abou El Fadl (2014). *Reasoning with God: Reclaiming Shari'ah in the Modern Age* London: Rowman & Littlefield, p. 297.

On another occasion, the Qur'ānic verse reads:

And verily, We have sent among every Ummah (community, nation) a Messenger (proclaiming): "Worship Allah (Alone), and avoid (or keep away from) Taghut (all false deities, etc. i.e. do not worship Taghut besides Allah)." Then of them were some whom Allah guided and of them were some upon whom the straying was justified. So travel through the land and see what was the end of those who denied (the truth). Q. 16: 36.

Classical scholarship refers to the above verse as the knowledge of the divine traditions or the knowledge of the science of religious politics, as shown in the above diagram. As one might observe, life itself was not created in vain. Rather, it was subject to traditions and laws, and human beings were commanded in their meeting and what was expressed in it from the conflict and civil strife. And what follows injustice from war, contest, king, sovereignty, and civilized circulation is carried out in a straightforward way and established rules, and whoever suffers from them loses, even if they were friend or prophet, and on this, the Muslims' defeats come out in the Battle of Uhud, and at the beginning of the Battle of Hunayn, and their defeats will graduate on multiple levels.

The rise of historical philosophy as a field of study

Ibn Khaldūn is the main source of historiography, and orientalism in the medieval, despite more than one thousand writings about his opinions many scholars are unaware of his dignity and they think historiography did not continue after Thucydides and Herodotus and stopped in ancient, therefore a place of Islamic historiography in medieval, it has not yet been determined, while the existence of Ibn Khaldūn is sufficient to prove it as an international paradigm. He uses the term humanities based on the empirical reason for the first time in his book, *al-Muqadimmah*, he explained the evolution of civilization by natural causes centuries before Giambattista Vico Marie Arouet/ Voltaire (d. 1778),¹⁰ Baron de La Brède et de Montesquieu (d. 1755),¹¹ Auguste Comte (d. 1857),¹² Any orientalist, for example, Gibb (d. 1895), considered Ibn Khaldūn as an oriental theorist, the father of sociology who developed humanities with Western secularism a few centuries earlier than Europe.¹³

¹⁰ Ira O. Wade (2016). *Intellectual Development of Voltaire* Princeton University Press, pp. 330-331.

¹¹ Stephen Gaukroger (2020). *Civilization and the Culture of Science: Science and the Shaping of Modernity, 1795-1935* Oxford: oxford University Press, p. 52.

¹² Thomas F. Noble (1994). *Civilization and the Culture of Science: Science and the Shaping of Modernity, 1795-1935* Boston: Cengage Learning, p. 196.

¹³ Robert Irwin (2019). *Ibn Khaldun: An Intellectual Biography* Princeton University Press, p. 177; William R. Poll (1962). *Studies on the Civilization of Islam* Boston: Beacon Press, p. 152.

Ibn Khaldūn is considered the first to use the term "philosophy of history,"¹⁴ as he intended to distance himself from narration and record events without interconnecting them, as he intended to explain historical events. Islamic thinkers believe that Muslims were the first to lay the nucleus of this knowledge when they were following in the direction of the Book of God and looking at the horizons, in compliance with the Almighty's saying,

And verily, We have sent among every Ummah (community, nation) a Messenger (proclaiming): "Worship Allah (Alone), and avoid (or keep away from) Taghut (all false deities, etc. i.e. do not worship Taghut besides Allah)." Then of them were some whom Allah guided and of them were some upon whom the straying was justified. So travel through the land and see what was the end of those who denied (the truth). Q. 16: 36.

The glory of Islamic civilization disappeared, the West took it over, and they continued Ibn Khaldūn's journey of researching this approach and methodology.¹⁵ This science may be unknown to many who are interested in research and investigation, but it is a basic science and a methodological tool for Renaissance and decision-makers, as it sets a solid ground for them, not with regard to understanding the past, but with regard to extrapolating the present and the future.¹⁶ This scientific research tool provides multiple perspectives to political and societal actors, assisting them in understanding the renaissance movement in societies.¹⁷

Because of the need for objectivity in science, this research must not see the ideas provided in this field as isolated pieces that are unrelated, but rather as different methods of knowing that should be presented and studied in depth in concert. Through the study of the philosophy of history, each of these parts deals with an aspect of the vital topic, which the interested person devotes to detail. From this scientific need, the interest of the renewed researcher is to introduce this knowledge and facilitate its investigations for activists in various religious bodies and the public. For tracing the impact of their writings, studies, and research on society, the cultural community uses its lexicon of research encyclopaedias, book classifications, and scientific heritage, particularly in the field of the subject, to mandate the creation of writings, studies, and investigations.

¹⁴ Jeremy Kleidosty (2016). *The Concert of Civilizations: The Common Roots of Western and Islamic Constitutionalism Rethinking Political and International Theory* London; New York: Routledge, p. 120; Muhsin Mahdi (2015). *Ibn Khaldūn's Philosophy of History: A Study in the Philosophic Foundation of the Science of Culture* London; New York: Routledge; Roy Jackson (2014). *What is Islamic Philosophy?* London: Routledge.

¹⁵ Louay M. Safi (2022). *Islam and the Trajectory of Globalization: Rational Idealism and the Structure of World History* New York: Routledge, pp. 171-172; Firas Alkhateeb (2017). *Lost Islamic History: Reclaiming Muslim Civilization from the Past* London: Oxford University Press, pp. 190-193.

¹⁶ See, Erik Ringmar (2019). *History of International Relations: A Non-European Perspective* Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2019.

¹⁷ Marinos Sariyannis (2018). *A History of Ottoman Political Thought up to the Early Nineteenth Century* Leiden: Brill, see in particular chapter 6, "Khaldunian Philosophy: Innovation Justified", pp. 279-324.

Muslim scientists laid the foundations of modern physics long before anybody else. Ibn Khaldūn resumed his voyage of scientific exploration and experimentation in the West after they abandoned this knowledge, which had been the source of their civilization's greatness. Although many individuals are unfamiliar with this science, the Renaissance creators and decision-makers of the time relied on it since it laid a firm foundation for them in the present reality. The theories described in this science really should not be viewed as isolated and disconnected pieces but rather as multiple approaches to understanding that complement and encourage each other. This science provides society's leaders with multiple perspectives for acknowledging the Renaissance movement in their societies. Each of them focuses on a different facet of this fascinating subject: history's philosophy. The Qur'ānic demand and reasonable expectation are two things that really should be recognized from an Islamic perspective.

The relevance of the Qur'ānic stories and events regarding previous nations realize the significance of this demand from the Qur'ān to be considered. If they were among the people of mind, when describing the conditions of those nations, such as the luxury of living, piety and truth, disbelief of God, setbacks of instinct, and reversal of perception, and how they were devastated and traumatized by their civilization, It is fourteen hundred years old and shows the truth, the Almighty, in the folds of those stories or a commentary on them, the legislation of God in His righteousness and the laws that govern this life and are directed at it to show the causes of the decline and the reasons for growth and carry on.¹⁸

As stated by Imad al-Din Khalil, the Noble Qur'ān brings its historical data to move the human being towards the goals set by Islam and at the same time separate the human, as an individual or group, from the pitfalls and zigzags that have led to the fate of tens or even hundreds of nations, groups, and peoples.¹⁹

Our history, in particular, is more true to the influences of Islam, to the ability of this religion to reformulate the mind and conscience. And

¹⁸ Yvonne Yazbeck Haddad (1982). *Contemporary Islam and the Challenge of History* New York: SUNY Press, pp. 105-106.

¹⁹ *Ibid*, pp. 104-105.

it goes on to clarify the dialectical relationship between the Noble Qur'an and historiographical facts.²⁰

In addition, in elaboration, Khalil indicates that:

The Qur'anic dealings with history take forms ranging between direct presentation and narrative narration of the experiences of several human groups, and between an extract that is characterized by the focus and intensity of the historical laws that govern the human movement in time and space. If we add to this and that those verses and Qur'anic passages related to the era of the message, we will become more aware of the dimensions of the spaces granted by the Holy Qur'an for history.²¹

With an emphasis on the Noble Qur'an, Imad al-Din Khalil analyzes it with three axes: historical events, the emergence and rise of civilizations, and the degradation and collapse of civilizations. Each of these axes is supported by dense swarms of words that nearly completely illuminate the bulk of their regions.²² He soon discloses the extent of the interconnectedness of the factors of Islam with the movement of history in general, by saying:

Islam represents a position at the apex of the movement of history because it is an invitation to discover the laws of movement and conforms to them, not only with the movement of history, as Marxism seeks, but with the laws of the universe and the whole world.²³

Perhaps the best summary of the approach of the Noble Qur'an is the words of Almighty God: We will show them Our Signs in the universe and their own selves until it becomes manifest to them that this (the Qur'an) is the truth. Is it not sufficient in regard to your Lord that He is a Witness over all things? Q. 41: 43.

The second is the rational demand. Identical laws govern the universe, and the process of human life as a commitment to values or a deviation from the right rules, and the proven seriousness are almost repeated images. Therefore, it is necessary and imperative for any human group to seek change and realize the values of truth and virtue. This is because human history is a series of facts that take each other into perspective and do not cease to exist, even if they differ in form. The person who cannot pass it does not start from zero but rather from a negative action. Because the experiences of humanity are communal property, whoever benefits from it has succeeded in the required manner and plunged into the mire of bankruptcy and perceived failure by those who tried to establish and let go of it.

²⁰ Imād al-Dīn Khalīl (2001). *Madkhal 'ilā al-Tārīkh w-al-Ḥadhārah al-Islāmiyyah* (Introduction to Islamic History and Civilization) Kuala Lumpur: International Islamic University Malaysia, p.5.

²¹ Ibid, p. 6.

²² Ibid, p.9.

²³ Imād al-Dīn Khalīl (1985). *Mu'ashirāt Islāmiyyah fī Zaman al-Sur'ah* (Islamic Indications in the time of Speed) Beirut: Mu'asassat al-Risālah, p. 20.

State and Social Solidarity (al-'Aṣabiyyah) of Ibn Khaldūn:

He was the first to read history in a different way since history had previously been examined as a series of distinct and sequential events.²⁴ Ibn Khaldūn made history a field for induction, analysis, and conclusion, and he intended to deduce the laws that govern the historical movement so that they could even be used in other areas.²⁵ In history, he considered historical facts and attributions, and the actualization of historical events as the domain of material industry. Ibn Khaldūn's role was to work with and develop laws from the material.²⁶

Observing the cycle from victory to extinction and stressing the theory of social solidarity (al-'Aṣabiyyah) based on blood, religion, or any other social bond in all stages; he was able to develop a theory about the emergence and stability of the state, its decomposition, and its extinction through this study.²⁷ When it came to writing history, correcting facts, and examining the phenomena of human civilization, Ibn Khaldūn's first priority was to address a crucial question: how does the state grow and fall? He also considered the fact that states, like persons, have natural lifespans.²⁸

The life cycle of the state. Ibn Khaldūn viewed the state as a living organism that is born, grows, and then ages to perish.²⁹ The state has a lifetime just like a living being.³⁰ Ibn Khaldūn links it to the human life cycle mentioned in the Qur'ān saying:

Allah is He Who created you in (a state of) weakness, then gave you strength after weakness, then after strength gave (you) weakness and grey hair. He creates what He wills. And it is He Who is the All-Knowing, the All-Powerful (i.e. Able to do all things). Q. 30: 54.

According to Ibn Khaldūn, the state passes through four stages:³¹

1. The victory and seizer of authority developed conquest, subjugation, and conquest
2. The developed tyranny and monopoly of power and denial of the league.
3. Developed the void, fame, and benevolence to collect the fruits of the ruler and, in it, prevail comfort and reassurance.
4. Old age/advanced in years, and extinction developed due to extravagance and squandering

²⁴ Majid Khadduri (1984). *The Islamic Conception of Justice* Baltimore; London: Johns Hopkins University Press, pp. 176-177.

²⁵ I.M.N. Al-Jubouri (2004). *History of Islamic Philosophy: With View of Greek Philosophy and Early History of Islam* Hertford: Authors Online Ltd, pp. 423-425.

²⁶ Ibn Khaldun (d. 808/1406). *Al-Muqaddimah/Introduction to Ibn Khaldun*, ed. Abu 'Abdullah al-Sa'īd, Beirut: Dar Iḥyā' al-Turāth al-Islāmī, 2015, p. 38.

²⁷ Syed Farid Alatas (2017). "Ibn Khaldun (1332-1406)", in Syed Farid Alatas, Vineeta Sinha, *Sociological Theory Beyond the Canon* London: Palgrave, pp. 22-23.

²⁸ Fuad Baali (1988). *Society, State, and Urbanism: Ibn Khaldun's Sociological Thought* Albany: State University of New York Press, pp. 81-82.

²⁹ Ibn Khaldun (1958). *The Muqaddimah: An Introduction to History*, tr. Franz Rosenthal New York: Pantheon Books, vol. 2, pp. 106-107; Robert Irwin (2019). *Ibn Khaldun: An Intellectual Biography* Princeton: Princeton University Press, pp. 83-85; C. Chase-Dunn, E. Anderson (2005). *The Historical Evolution of World-Systems Evolutionary Processes in World Politics* New York: Palgrave, pp. 12-13.

³⁰ Zainab MalmĒd al-KhudairĒ (2006). *Philosophy of History for Ibn Khaldun* Dar al-Farābī, p. 185; Ra'fat Ghunaymī Shaykh (1986). *Contemporary Modern Arabs History* Cairo: Dar al-Thaqāfah, p. 4; 'Abd al-'Azīz al-Dūrī (2005). *The Emergence of History Science among the Arabs* Beirut Markaz Dirāsāt al-Waḥdah al-'Arabīyah, p. 17; Sulaymān Khaṭīb (1993). *The Philosophy of Civilization for Malik ibn Nabi: an Islamic Study in Light of Contemporary Reality* Sharjah: a;l-Mu'asassah al-Jāmi'iyyah lil-Dirāsāt, p. 58; M. Umer Chapra (2015). *Muslim Civilization: The Causes of Decline and the Need for Reform* Markfield: Kube Publishing Ltd, pp. 17-23.

³¹ Ibn Khaldun (d. 808/1406). *Al-Muqaddimah/Introduction to History*, pp. 289-300; Fuad Baali (1988). *Society, State, and Urbanism: Ibn Khaldun's Sociological Thought*, p. 81.

1. The victory and seizure of authority developed conquest, subjugation, and conquest.
2. The developed tyranny and monopoly of power and the denial of the league.
3. They created the void, fame, and benevolence in order to collect the ruler's fruits and install comfort and reassurance in them.
4. Old age or advanced in years, and extinction developed due to extravagance and squandering.³²

Ibn Khaldūn's thought on the state and civilization revolves around the law of social solidarity/*al-'aṣabiyah*, meaning the cohesion between relatives, tribes, and clans, which pays for advocacy and demands for rule and conquers for its sake. It breaches swearing allegiance, loyalty, and other forms of agglomeration and tribal alliance, including any kind of loyalty that leads to overstepping or overcompensating for the sake of that end. Ibn Khaldūn studies how a group reaches the overthrow of a regime, and then what happens to it when it comes to power and intensifies its strength.³³

Ibn Khaldūn studies how a group reaches the overthrow of a regime, then what happens to it when it comes to power and strengthens its power, and what happens upon collapse. In his theory, he emphasizes the social solidarity (*al-'aṣabiyah*) theory based on blood or religion. If *al-'aṣabiyah* is found, then its interpretation of the phenomena is based on it. When it becomes stronger, its owners gain power, and when it reaches them, power, this bond weakens gradually until this system collapses and a new system is established. Although this model that Ibn Khaldūn talks about, as defined in his study, is related to the countries of the Maghreb/greater Morocco that he anticipated and the kingdoms that were established within, the theory of social solidarity/*al-'aṣabiyah* is a correct theory in its essence and applies to many places.³⁴

The individual in the tribe is more closely related to his siblings than to one father, from among the closest cousins, so their own lineage settles these, and they share with the others. The lineage does not merely belong to a common ancestor but rather belongs to a specific group. This is what made Muḥammad 'Ābid al-Jābirī define *al-'aṣabiyah* as:

A sociological, emotional, and unconscious association that binds members of a group based on kinship.³⁵

This is true of more than just blood ties-based tribes. It applies to a political party if its members meet this requirement, and it applies to an army that transforms into a political party with this link. What is meant by social solidarity is the presence of a link that binds a group of people together and motivates them to rally, solidarity, and a sense of mutual danger in the face of others/*al-'aṣabiyah*.

³² Qais Ḥāim, Hānā al-Janabi (2016). *Philosophy of History* Amman: al-Dar al-Minhajiyah, p. 86; Nizār 'Uyūn al-Sūd (1996). *The Emergence and Development of Psycho-social thought among the Arabs* Damascus: Ittihād al-Kuttāb al-'Arab, p. 195; Muḥammad Ū'ha Badawi (2000). *Al-Manhaj al-Siyāsī* Alexandria: al-Maktab al-Jāmi'ā al-Ḥadīth, pp. 29-31 Robert Irwin (2019). *Ibn Khaldun: An Intellectual Biography*, p. 5.

³³ Ibn Khaldun (d. 808/1406). *Al-Muqadimmah/Introduction* to Ibn Khaldun, p. 266.

³⁴ Muḥammad 'Ābid al-Jābirī (2011). *Ibn Khaldun's Thought: Social Solidarity and the State* (Fikir ibn Khaldun; al-'Aṣabiyya wa-l-Dawlah) Beirut: Markis Dirāsāt al-Wiḥdih al-'Arabiyya, p. 254; Sāṭi' al-Ḥuṣārī (1961). *Studies on the Introduction of Ibn Khaldun* (Dirāsāt 'an Muqadimita ibn Khaldun) Cairo: Maktab al-Khānjī, p. 33.

³⁵ Muḥammad 'Ābid al-Jābirī (1979). *Ibn Khaldun's Thought: 'Aṣabiyya and the State: Milestones of Khaldun's Theory in Islamic History* Casablanca: Moroccan Publishing House, p. 253.

Accordingly, Muḥammed ‘Ābid al-Jābirī says:

Modern conglomerates, in all their forms, can be considered nervous when their affiliates strive to achieve certain clear goals, and their affiliation to the bloc reflects a strong sense of solidarity for achievement that intensifies in times of danger and grows steadily.³⁶

In addition, in Ibn Khaldūn’s opinion, if the religious sectarian is associated with religion, nothing stands before it.³⁷ The religious character eliminates the competition and envy that are in the people of (ethnic) social solidarity/*al-‘aṣabiyah*, the uniqueness of the approach to the truth, as he believes that another solidarity, must bind religion.³⁸ The implication of this view is, in fact, that religion does not dispense with a group or organization that demands its fulfillment and defends it. The existence of a group or party that carries and adopts this religious idea achieves two interests: the first is the existence of social solidarity, with which the defense is carried out, and the physical body (the group) that defends it. The second is the existence of the idea (religion) that evokes, refines, and spends social solidarity/*al-‘aṣabiyah*) from the impurities produced by fanaticism. As religion purifies the - *‘aṣabiyah* from its negative and invests in its positive.³⁹

Factors weakening social solidarity/*al-‘aṣabiyah*

There are two factors that weaken social solidarity (*al-‘aṣabiyah*); the first factor is submission and docile.⁴⁰ The second factor is luxury and pleasure. For Ibn Khaldūn, if there is a nation or a society in which the tribal bond, i.e., social solidarity, is present, there are common goals; with these common goals, there is an element of religion, and Islamic societies contain people and religion, then what eliminates the effect of religion.⁴¹

³⁶ Muḥammad ‘Ābid al-Jābirī (2011). *Ibn Khaldun’s Thought: Social Solidarity and the State* (Fikir ibn Khaldun; al-‘Aṣabiyya wa-l-Dawlah), p. 183.

³⁷ Fuad Baali (2005). *The Science of Human Social Organization: Conflicting Views on Ibn Khaldun’s (1332-1406) ilm al-Imran (the science of social organization)* Lewiston, New York: Edwin Mellen Press, pp. 7-8.

³⁸ See, Zaid Ahmad (2004). *The Epistemology of Ibn Khaldun Culture and Civilization in the Middle East* London; New York: Routledge, particularly chapter four, "The Intellectual Sciences (al-‘Ulum al-‘Aqliyya)".

³⁹ Kamal Mirawdeli (2015). *Asabiyya and State: A Reconstruction of Ibn Khaldun’s Philosophy of History* Bloomington: Author House, 2015; Syed Farid Alatas (2017). "Ibn Khaldun (1332-1406)", in Syed Farid Alatas, Vineeta Sinha, *Sociological Theory Beyond the Canon*, pp. 17-18.

⁴⁰ Ra’fat al-Sheikh (2000). *Tafsīr Masār al-Tārīkh* (Interpretation of the Course of History) Cairo: Mu’assasat ‘Aīn lil-Dirāsāt wa-l-Buḥūth, p. 84.

⁴¹ Ibn Khaldun (d. 808/1406). *al-Muqadimah* Beirut: Dar al-Fikir, p. 182.

Ibn Khaldūn explains two factors that paralyze the activity of social solidarity and cancel its role, namely submission and docility.⁴² Since humiliation and submission are two of the most powerful breakers of social solidarity and its intensity, their submission and humiliation are evidence of the loss of social solidarity, and they did not feel the humiliation until they were unable to defend it, and whoever is unable to defend it is more important than whoever is unable to claim and resist it. If one is unable to defend oneself, it is preferable to be unable to demand and reject one's position.⁴³

The second factor of luxury and bliss, a factor that stops *al-'aṣābiyah*, is its way toward achieving its desired goal.⁴⁴ The more the members of the *al-'aṣābiyah* indulged in pleasure, the weaker their bond gradually until it dissolved. The Holy Qur'ān has drawn our attention to the role of luxury and pleasure in the destruction of nations.

And when We decide to destroy a town (population), We (first) send a definite order (to obey Allah and be righteous) to those among them [or We (first) increase in number those of its population] who are given the good things of this life. Then, they transgress therein, and thus the word (of torment) is justified against it (them). Then We destroy it with complete destruction. Q. 17: 16.

If this system enters an intellectual system that works like a virus that is taking out the defense revolution and leads to submission and decile, then it is more appropriate for the issue of claim and resistance to end. This is important for the leaders of the Renaissance to realize where the imbalance in building the awakening comes from. The existence of the human mass, according to Ibn Khaldun's theory, which has a bond and a religion, is supposed to be able to effect transformations, but if the factor of submission and decile enters this system, it denies its ability to effect change. If a system of submission and decile is added to a system that leads to luxury, and indulgence in pleasures, materials, and worldly benefits, the issue of defense ends, and *al-'aṣābiyah* loses its meaning.⁴⁵

On the other hand, there are two factors that are crucial in strengthening *al-'aṣābiyah* and supporting its connections. The first is the presence of general *'aṣābiyah*, which transcends *al-'aṣābiyah* of lineage and goes beyond social or spiritual cohesion, because the great states need general *'aṣābiyah*, while the smallest states need nothing more than the *'aṣābiyah* lineage.⁴⁶ Second, the occurrence of the state being overthrown in the aging phase or process Ibn Khaldūn believes that this is not an inevitable or inevitable consequence. The existing state will age if its bond is based on the *'aṣābiyah* lineage. It cannot stand for long before a strong *'aṣābiyah* demand, especially when this *'aṣābiyah* is reinforced by a religious vocation, changes the existing conditions. There is not merely a call for a better situation, but rather a material force (a band) that supports it.⁴⁷

⁴² Fuad Baali (1988). *Society, State, and Urbanism: Ibn Khaldun's Sociological Thought*, p. 84.

⁴³ Ibid, pp. 53-54; Bogdan Mieczkowski (1987). "Ibn Khaldun's Fourteenth Century View of Bureaucracy", *American Journal of Islamic Social Sciences*, volume 4, no. 2, pp. 193-194.

⁴⁴ Ibn Khaldun (d. 808/1406). *al-Muqaddimah*, pp. 155-156.

⁴⁵ Muḥammad 'Ābid al-Jābrī (2011). *Ibn Khaldun's Thought: Social Solidarity and the State* (Fikir Ibn Khaldun; al-'Aṣābiyya wa-l-Dawlah), p. 257.

⁴⁶ Fuad Baali (2005). *The Science of Human Social Organization: Conflicting Views on Ibn Khaldun's (1332-1406) 'ilm al-'Ūmran (science of social organization)*, pp. 38-39; Syed Farid Alatas (2017). "Ibn Khaldun (1332-1406)", in Syed Farid Alatas, Vineeta Sinha, *Sociological Theory Beyond the Canon*, pp. 18-20.

⁴⁷ Muḥammad 'Ābid al-Jābrī (2011). *Ibn Khaldun's Thought: Social Solidarity and the State*, p. 257.

The *'asabiyah* needs a bond, and it needs a religion or an idea.⁴⁸ Removing these two matters and neutralizing the *'asabiyah* process requires introducing a system that leads to submission and decile.⁴⁹ In addition, a system that leads to luxury and immersion in worldly affairs when the first system (the league) is of no use.⁵⁰ The implications of Ibn Khaldūn have great meaning in contemporary reality.⁵¹ It is necessary for states and societies to ensure that the *'asabiyah* of lineage extends beyond the realm of social and spiritual cohesiveness.⁵² Large countries need general *'asabiyah*, while small countries need nothing more than *'asabiyah*.⁵³ If we want to enhance *'asabiyah* and strengthen its ties in large societies, we need more than just genealogy.⁵⁴ In order to achieve a large-scale fusion amongst several races that are not tied by blood connections, countries like the United States complete their citizenship, nationalism, or supranationalism.⁵⁵ Because of this, Islam has a powerful *'asabiyah*, which binds together people of different races, colors, and languages. As Ibn Khaldūn indicated that:

The religious vocation increases the state's power in its origin over the strength of the *'asabiyah*/sectarianism that had more than its number.⁵⁶

What is said about states can be said in one way or another about parties, institutions, and groups, just as the individual ages and the state ages,⁵⁷ so the organization may age. Organizations and institutions also have a life cycle. It starts with a nascent idea that has not yet matured, then the bully begins to push this idea, and it grows and crystallizes, and its goals are determined.⁵⁸ Then it reaches the stage of youth with all the meaning that the word

⁴⁸ Steven C. Catopn (1990). "Anthropological Theories of Tribe and State Formation in the Middle East: Ideology and Semiotics of Power", in Philip Shukry Khoury, Joseph Kostiner (1990). *Tribes and State Formation in the Middle East* Berkeley: University of California Press, pp. 85-87.

⁴⁹ Bassam Tibi (1997). *Arab Nationalism: Between Islam and the Nation-State* London: Macmillan, 1997, p. 140.

⁵⁰ See, Muhsin Mahdi (2015). *Ibn Khaldūn's Philosophy of History: A Study in the Philosophic Foundation of the Science of Culture* London; New York: Routledge, in particular chapter three, "From History to the Science of Culture".

⁵¹ Bassam Tibi (1997). *Arab Nationalism: Between Islam and the Nation-State*, pp. 140-142.

⁵² Linda T. Darling (2007). "Social Cohesion ('Asabiyya) and Justice in the Late Medieval Middle East", *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 329-357.

⁵³ Noah Feldman (2012). *The Fall and Rise of the Islamic State* New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 2012, pp. 42-43

⁵⁴ Ibn Khaldun (1958). *The Muqaddimah: An Introduction to History*, tr. Franz Rosenthal, vol. 1, p. 105.

⁵⁵ Ibn Khaldun (d. 808/1406). *al-Muqaddimah* Beirut: Dar al-Fikir, pp. 170-171

⁵⁶ *Ibid*, p. 170.

⁵⁷ *Ibid*, p. 382.

⁵⁸ Ibn Khaldun (1958). *The Muqaddimah: An Introduction to History*, tr. Franz Rosenthal, vol. 1, p. 46.

carries, expressing enthusiasm, strength, and hope.⁵⁹ These goals will be clear. If the movement is not able to achieve its goals and strikes it in a way that hinders it psychologically and practically, then it is exposed to the aging /old age phase. The ceiling of the goals diminishes, as does the intensity and clarity of the idea, and the emotion of youth diminishes.⁶⁰ Either for the absence of a common goal or for not seeking to achieve it through the psychological disabilities that have occurred and the predominance of matters of life and living over thinking.⁶¹

As has been the case throughout history, these movements, both Islamic and non-Islamic, begin with an idea that is fruitful and grows into something powerful and youthful. In the case of others' success or failure, they begin to feel the effects of age more acutely. It will flourish as long as it retains its passion and concentration. However, as its scope narrows, it fades and deteriorates. A fresh group of young people enters and pursues the same objective, either succeeds or fails in the same way, and this continues indefinitely.

The life cycle of movements and parties

Among the most dangerous things is the time for the movement or the mainstream to be prolonged without achieving its goal. The historical depth of any mainstream earns it great

⁵⁹ Fuad Baali (1988). *Society, State, and Urbanism: Ibn Khaldun's Sociological Thought*, pp. 71-72

⁶⁰ Abdelkader Dajaghoul (1989). *al-Ishkâiyât al-Târîkhiyyah fî 'Ilm al-Ijtimâ' al-Siyāsâ 'and Ibn Khaldûn* (The Historical Problematic of Ibn Khaldoun's Political and Social Sciences) tr. (Ibn Khaldoun: mode d'emploi. Les problèmes d'un heritage), Fayçal 'Abbâs Beirut: Dar al-Ĥadâthah, p. 133.

⁶¹ Fida Mohamad (1998). Ibn Khaldun's Theory of Social Change: A Comparison with Hegel, Marx and Durkheim", *American Journal of Islamic Social Sciences*, Summer, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 43-44.

legitimacy and popularity, in the event that it moves from goal to goal and goes one-step after another. In the event that he fails and is unable to climb the ladder of goals, this usually has a negative impact. As the historical depth of the movement becomes a burden for it, it always falls under the hammer of questions about its successes over such a long period. In addition, the effects and ghosts of defeat are often a psychological obstacle before taking a new course.

This balance of experience and motivation may be used to encourage the continuing and the drive to keep providing in order to prevent aging. When the historical leaders of the youth make sure that they fully play their role, as was the case when Prophet Muhammad assigned Usama ibn Zayd, who was only seventeen at the time, to be commander of the Muslim army in a crucial battle to discipline the Romans, it is sufficient to maintain the vitality of any system.⁶² The key axis to avoid sliding and leaving employees dependent on others throughout the world is to conceive about being self-sufficient and independent when the chance occurs, as well as to continue working to attain those goals. This is how a regimen may be reenergized on an ongoing basis.⁶³

Ibn Khaldūn's methodology

Ibn Khaldūn's methodology focuses on states, as he does not look at large systems because he looks at states in their different conditions.⁶⁴ He sees in his model of the tribe that when it is not in power, it possesses roughness and bonds, and if a religious affection calls for it, then it takes off, and nothing stops it from overthrowing an existing situation.⁶⁵ He also sees that when this tribe arrives and members of it take advantage of luxury and pleasure, the process of weakness in its circles begins. The factors of aging break down, the bond on which it was established dissolves, and those who are not in its league enter it and gradually begin to collapse.⁶⁶

Ibn Khaldūn's view of the states, and the states that he saw were the small states that were established as kingdoms.⁶⁷ Nevertheless, the idea of '*aṣābiyah*,' the idea of submission and docility, and the idea of luxury and pleasure are good ideas that many nations use in various fields of conflict.⁶⁸ The leader must understand this trilogy (factors that weaken social solidarity/*al-ʿaṣābiyah*) well enough to set out to research the pages of history in order to make sure that this system has evidence from history and reality.⁶⁹

The scientific employment of '*aṣābiyah* law that the various parties' institutions and governments must strive to renew its vitality; otherwise, they will become old and perish.⁷⁰ The emergence of new, young groups, institutions, and governments will guarantee the progress of the project.⁷¹ Moreover, the fact that it does not carry advanced historical impulsive pain, and hence we realize the value of the multiplicity of parties and institutions.⁷² As the historical legacy sometimes has a disincentive role, for fear of recurring pain. Aging comes from rigidity of ideas, weak connection (*ʿaṣābiyah*), abundance of luxury and pleasure,

⁶² Zaydān Jirjī (2020). *Tārīkh al-Tamadun al-Islāmī* (History of Islamic Civilization) Beirut: Dār al-Qalam, vol. 1, p. 24.

⁶³ Muḥammad Riyāḍ al-Dīn al-Rayyīs (1979). *al-Naẓariyāt al-Siyāsiyya al-Islāmiyya* (Islamic Political Theories Cairo: Dar al-Turāth, pp. 302-303.

⁶⁴ Fuad Baali (1988). *Society, State, and Urbanism: Ibn Khaldun's Sociological Thought*, p. 21.

⁶⁵ Martínez Enamorado Virgolio (2006). "Knowledge, power, and madrasas at the time of Ibn Khaldun," in Ana Serrano et al. (eds.), *Ibn Khaldun. The Mediterranean in the 14th Century. Rise and Fall of Empires*, exhibition catalog Seville: Real Alcázar of Seville, pp. 349-351; Syed Farid Alatas (2017). "Ibn Khaldun (1332-1406)", in Syed Farid Alatas, Vineeta Sinha, *Sociological Theory Beyond the Canon*, pp. 36-37.

⁶⁶ See, Muhsin Mahdi (2015). *Ibn Khaldūn's Philosophy of History: A Study in the Philosophic Foundation of the Science of Culture* London; New York: Routledge, in particular chapter three, "From History to the Science of Culture".

⁶⁷ Badrane Benlahcene (2013). *The Socio-Intellectual Foundations of Malek Bennabi's Approach to Civilization* Herndon: International Institute of Islamic Thought (IIIT), pp. 192-193.

⁶⁸ Fuad Baali (1988). *Society, State, and Urbanism: Ibn Khaldun's Sociological Thought*, p. 72.

⁶⁹ Syed Farid Alatas (2017). "Ibn Khaldun (1332-1406)", in Syed Farid Alatas, Vineeta Sinha, *Sociological Theory Beyond the Canon* London: Palgrave, pp. 15-17.

⁷⁰ John A. Hall (1986). *Powers and Liberties: The Causes and Consequences of the Rise of the West* Berkeley: University of California Press, pp. 93-95.

⁷¹ Bruce B. Lawrence (1984). *Ibn Khaldun and Islamic Ideology* Leiden: E.J. Brill, p. 9.

⁷² Muhsin Mahdi (2015). *Ibn Khaldūn's Philosophy of History: A Study in the Philosophic Foundation of the Science of Culture*, pp. 196-199.

and distance from real goals, as it comes from submission and decile.⁷³ Complete without awareness and foresight what looks like a state of surrender.⁷⁴ The coalitions and alliances that depend on agreeing on one idea and one goal, regardless of blood ties, are among the strongest groups, and they must be pursued in our societies instead of flaking, splitting, and fragmenting movements that seek revival.⁷⁵

Islam is one of the ingredients that give tremendous power to any group that adopts it. It is necessary to strengthen *al-'aṣabiyyah*.⁷⁶ It obliterates any *'aṣabiyyah* based on race or ethnical background, which prevents conflict and failure.⁷⁷ As the following Qur'ānic verses read,

And hold fast, all of you together, to the Rope of Allah (i.e. this Qur'an), and be not divided among yourselves, and remember Allah's Favour on you, for you were enemies one to another but He joined your hearts together, so that, by His Grace, you became brethren (in Islamic Faith), and you were on the brink of a pit of Fire, and He saved you from it. Thus Allah makes His Ayat (proofs, evidences, verses, lessons, signs, revelations, etc.) clear to you, that you may be guided. Q. 3: 103.

Verily! Allah commands that you should render back the trusts to those, to whom they are due; and that when you judge between men, you judge with justice. Verily, how excellent is the teaching which He (Allah) gives you! Truly, Allah is Ever All-Hearer, All-Seer. Q. 4: 58.

O you who believe! Obey Allah and obey the Messenger (Muhammad), and those of you (Muslims) who are in authority. (And) if you differ in anything amongst yourselves, refer it to Allah and His Messenger, if you believe in Allah and in the Last Day. That is better and more suitable for final determination. Q. 4: 59

The hierarchy of corrupt parties, whether governmental or not, is a golden opportunity for the emergence of a new - *'aṣabiyyah* based on religion as a chosen central idea, to bring about processes of change and social transformation. A practical example of the content of this historical accomplishment based on manifestations of religious *'aṣabiyyah* is the Almoravid State (Murābiṭūn) during the reign of Yūsuf ibn Tāshfīn.⁷⁸

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⁷³ Bogdun Mieczkowski (1987). "Ibn Khaldun's Fourteenth Century View of Bureaucracy", *American Journal of Islamic Social Sciences*, volume 4, no. 2, pp. 193-194

⁷⁴ Syed Farid Alatas (2017). "Ibn Khaldun (1332-1406)", in Syed Farid Alatas, Vineeta Sinha, *Sociological Theory Beyond the Canon* London: Palgrave, pp. 22-23.

⁷⁵ Bruce B. Lawrence (1984). *Ibn Khaldun and Islamic Ideology*, pp. 10-11.

⁷⁶ Abdulla al-Ahsan (2002). "On History, Progress, and Civilization", *American Journal of Islamic Social Sciences*, vol. 19, no. 2, Spring, pp.54-56.

⁷⁷ al-Māwardī, Abū al-Ḥasan 'Alī ibn Muḥammad al-Baṣrī (d. 450/1058). *al-Aḥkām al-Sulṭāniyya* (The Laws Of Islamic Governance) ed. Aḥmad Mubārak Kuwait: Dar Ibn Qutaibah, 1989, p. 22.

⁷⁸ Ḥasan 'Alī Ḥasan (1980). *al-Ḥaḍārah al-Islāmiyya fī Bilād al-Maghrib wa-l-Andalus: 'Aṣr al-Murābiṭīn wa-l-Muwaḥḥidīn* (Islamic Civilization in Morocco and Andalusia, the era of the Almoravids and the Almohads) Cairo: Maktabat al-Khānjī, 68; 'Alī Muḥammad al-Ṣalābī (2007). *Ṣafaḥāt Mushriqah min Tārīkh al-Islāmī fī al-Shamāl al-Ifriqī* (Bright Pages of Islamic History in North Africa) Cairo: Dar ibn al-Jawzī, pp. 263-264.

As for Arnold Toynbee, in contrast to Ibn Khaldūn, Ibn Khaldūn looked at his study of the state, but Arnold Toynbee broadened his view from the state to civilizations.⁷⁹ He was a great admirer of Ibn Khaldūn's work, but he studied the state in a larger context, which is the context of civilizations.⁸⁰ He studied human civilizations to produce very important conclusions.⁸¹ His work *A Study of History* is a 12-volume universal history that took him forty years to complete, 1921-1961.⁸² The major law discussed by Toynbee is the law of challenge and response. In its discussion and explanation, he proposes a rich set of ideas.⁸³

Toynbee believes that civilizations, despite the presence of elements of unity in them in the so-called cultural assortment of societies, have a diversity of small units (states and societies) within this civilization system, and within these civilized societies, there is the creative human being. He thinks that civilizations, even though there are some parts of them that are the same, have a lot of different small units (states and societies) in them. In these civilized societies, there is a person who is creative.⁸⁴ These great innovators, such as prophets and messengers, or their class of philosophers and theorists, whose ideas were based on the foundations of massive societies, are the ones who founded civilizations or launched their growth.⁸⁵ He believes that this system, which is made up of the civilization system, the civilized states, and the states that fall within its framework and in its heart, are the creative people who lead these situations; societies undergo challenges and respond to them and develop their capabilities in order to overcome them.⁸⁶

Toynbee believes that the emergence and resurrection of civilizations has multiple causes.⁸⁷ One of the main things it is based on is how people and places react to challenges.

⁷⁹ Anthony Brundage (2017). *Going to the Sources: A Guide to Historical Research and Writing* Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons, p. 13.

⁸⁰ A.J. Toynbee (1936). *A Study of History* London: Oxford University Press, vol. 2, p. 322; Ra'fat al-Sheikh (2000). *Tafsīr Masār al-Tārīkh* (Interpretation of the Course of History), p. 194; Hāshim Yahyá Mallāh (1988). *Dirāsah fī Falsafat al-Tārīkh* (Studies in the Philosophy of History) Basra: Mudūriyat Dar al-Kutub, pp. 211-212.

⁸¹ Kirkpatrick Sale (2017). *Human Scale Revisited A New Look at the Classic Case for a Decentralist Future* Chelsea: Chelsea Green Publishing, pp. 64-66.

⁸² John Barker (1982). *The Super Historians: Makers of Our Past* Charles Scribner's, p. 269.

⁸³ 'Abdul-Jabār Nājī (2008). *Falsafat al-Tārīkh wa-l-Nihāyah al-Ḥatmiyyah lil-Dawalah* (Philosophy of History and the Inevitable End of Civilization and the State) Beirut: Mu'asassat al-'Ārif, p. 34.

⁸⁴ Ra'fat al-Sheikh (2000). *Tafsīr Masār al-Tārīkh* (Interpretation of the Course of History), pp. 191-192; Abdulla al-Ahsan (2002). "On History, Progress, and Civilization", *American Journal of Islamic Social Sciences*, vol. 19, no. 2, Spring, pp.54-55.

⁸⁵ A.J. Toynbee (1936). *A Study of History*, p. 61.

⁸⁶ Ibid, vol. 1, pp. 271-299; Muḥammad Ḍayf Allāh Baṭāyīnah(1983). *Fī Tārīkh al-Ḥaḍārah al-'Arabiyya al-Islāmiyyah* (In the History of the Arab-Islamic Civilization) Amman: Dar al-Furqān vol. 1, pp. 14-16; Ra'fat al-Sheikh (2000). *Tafsīr Masār al-Tārīkh* (Interpretation of the Course of History), pp. 196-197.

⁸⁷ Paul T. Phillips (2019). *Truth, Morality, and Meaning in History* Toronto: University of Toronto Press, pp. 76-77.

This drives them to come up with new ideas and move forward in their efforts to change cultures⁸⁸

According to the works of specialized scholars of Toynbee's historical thoughts, he indicated that human beings face a set of challenges (difficult situations, circumstances, and problems) on their way to building civilizations and deal with them either with successful responses that lead to their overcoming and the realization of the desired renaissance, up to civilization, or failed responses that do not lead to achieving renaissance and civilization.⁸⁹

Toynbee's divided the human challenges into two parts: the first is natural challenges, such as climate, physical geography, natural resources, geographical location, etc. The second is human challenges, such as the number and type of population, the culture and nature of societies.⁹⁰ Natural challenges may be difficult terrain, earthquakes, volcanoes, floods, and the like.⁹¹ Difficult terrain may encourage people to improve their skills, build roads and canals, and come up with new ways to get around.⁹² Likewise, the new virgin earth calls for people to develop their capabilities to exploit them, and there are motives for calamities, such as those great tragedies occur in society, whether these calamities are environmental or man-made. In both cases, a society faces very great challenges, and it must develop its capabilities to overcome them. These challenges face all nations without exception. The only difference is in the responses that differ from nation to nation. These responses determine the shape and type of results to be received.⁹³

In terms of the challenges, challenges are the secret of nations' rebirth. If there had not been challenges, civilizations would not have been formed, and people would not have been able to move around and find new places to live. Therefore, the desire for a life without challenges is tantamount to imprisoning a person's energies. As stated by Robert Schuler's *Power Ideas for a Happy Family*, conflict is the birthplace of the greatest creativity.⁹⁴ After a thousand years of complete darkness, they found a ray of hope and dispelled the absence of it caused by religious myths and national fanaticism. They are now on their way to a new space station armed with sci-fi technology. This is because, after the complete darkness that lasted for a thousand years, there was a ray of hope, and the absence of it was replaced by religious myths and national fanaticism. They felt that they found humankind in it too and started to struggle with nature to discover more of it. Goals that inspire humans by bestowing the most beautiful gifts in the form of achievements.⁹⁵ In addition, to this the Qur'an refers:

...And if Allah did not check one set of people by means of another, the earth would indeed be full of mischief. Q. 2: 251.

⁸⁸ Ra'fat al-Sheikh (2000). *Tafsīr Masār al-Tārīkh* (Interpretation of the Course of History), p. 196.

⁸⁹ Zayid Ma'lmĒd (1979). *Toynbee's Historical Biography* (Sirat al-Fikr al-Tārīkhī 'and Arnold Toynbee) Baghdad: Dar al-Ḥurīyyah, p. 72; Ḥusain Mu'nīs (1974). "Arnold Toynbee and the Theory of Challenge and Response" (Arnold Toynbee wa Naẓīrat al-Taḥādī wa-l-Istijābah), *Majalt al-'Arabī*, no. 182, January, p. 104.

⁹⁰ Graeme Snooks (2002). *The Laws of History* London and New York: Routledge, pp. 76-77.

⁹¹ Rudolf H. Moos, Moos, Rudolf H. (1976). *The Human Context: Environmental Determinants of Behavior* New York: Wiley, p. 8; Robert Angus Buchanan (1979). *History and Industrial Civilization* London: Macmillan International Higher Education, pp. 30-32.

⁹² See, Emĕrita S. Quito (2017). *Critique of Historical Theory* Mandaluyong: Anvil Publishing, Inc.

⁹³ Fu'ād Muḥammad Shibil (1968). *Toynbee's Historical Approach* (Manhaj Toynbee al-Tārīkhī) Cairo: Dar al-Kātib al-'Arabī, pp. 41-43.

⁹⁴ Robert Harold Schuller (1972). *Power Ideas for a Happy Family* New York: Pillar Books; Danny Cox and John Hoover (2002). *Leadership When the Heat's On* New York; McGraw-Hill, 194.

⁹⁵ Hishām Morsī, Wael 'Ādil, Aḥmad 'Ādil I 'Abdel Ḥakīm (2013). *Nonviolence War: The Third Option* (Ḥarb al-Lā 'Anf: al-Khayār al-Thālith) Cairo: Dar al-Bashīr, p. 58.

Arnold Toynbee, who may or may not be the person who came up with the idea of challenge and response, will be talked about so that we can better understand them.⁹⁶ He applied it to some of the dominant civilizations, and the defeated came to conclusions that met with acceptance and approval. That civilized growth is the dynamic of life and it is an act of active force in societies, and that the optimal challenge is the one that triggers a successful response, and so on.⁹⁷

According to Toynbee, the types of challenges in terms of their levels are divided into three main sections, harsh challenges, weak challenges, and creative challenges.⁹⁸ The harsh challenge is greater than the capacity of society, and human cannot develop mechanisms to overcome it,⁹⁹ such as the Inuit people and the constant snow challenge. Because they could not create anything to save them from this, their primitive life continued to this day. The weak challenge does not provoke a person to develop, and thus the person remains in the same state without progress.¹⁰⁰ Like the people of New Zealand, where the population is scarce, the resources are abundant and the land is easy, the indigenous people of New Zealand have not advanced.¹⁰¹ As for a creative challenge that provokes human energies, but any human being is able to develop mechanisms to overcome it, such as the case of all peoples who made civilizations, and developed their cognitive and practical mechanisms, until they were faced with an internal, external or environmental challenge and it could not continue or their movement slowed down, and preceded by others.¹⁰² It is this creative challenge that provokes the human energy to the maximum extent of planning, organization and mobilization.¹⁰³ The more a nation responds by developing its capabilities to meet a challenge, the more its capacity increases. Consequently, these peoples faced another challenge, so then overcame it to develop their energy. Thus, a developing, advanced and civilized society is formed, because of a series of challenges and successful responses.¹⁰⁴

⁹⁶ Toynbee, Arnold J (1947). *A Study of History* abridged edition by D. C. Somervell Oxford: Oxford University Press, vol. 1, pp. 106-107.

⁹⁷ Ḥusain Mu'nis (1974). "Arnold Toynbee and the Theory of Challenge and Response" (Arnold Toynbee wa Nazirat al-Taḥadī wa-l-Istijābah), *Majalt al-'Arabī*, no. 182, January, p. 104.

⁹⁸ Fu'ād Muḥammad Shibil (1968). *Toynbee's Historical Approach* (Manhaj Toynbee al-Tārīkhī), p. 47.

⁹⁹ Nevin Goma 'Alimm al-Din (1991). *The Philosophy of History for Arnold Toynbee* (Falasaft al-Tārīkh 'ind Arnold Toynbee Cairo: al-Hay'ah al-Maṣriyya al-'Āmmah li-Kitāb, pp. 138-139; Manal Khūrī (1960). *The Civilizational History of Toynbee* (al-Tārīkh al-Ḥadīthī 'ind Toynbee) Beirut: Dar al-'Ilm lil-Malāyīn, pp. 24-25.

¹⁰⁰ Arnold Joseph Toynbee, Daisaku Ikeda (1982). *The Toynbee-Ikeda Dialogue: Man Himself Must Choose* Tokyo: Kodansha International, pp. 75-76.

¹⁰¹ Ibid, p. 141.

¹⁰² A.J. Toynbee (1936). *A Study of History*, vol. 1, pp. 271-299; Ḥusain Mu'nis (1974). "Arnold Toynbee and the Theory of Challenge and Response" (Arnold Toynbee wa Nazirat al-Taḥadī wa-l-Istijābah), *Majalt al-'Arabī*, no. 182, January, p. 104; Manal Khūrī (1960). *The Civilizational History of Toynbee* (al-Tārīkh al-Ḥadīthī 'ind Toynbee), pp. 44-45.

¹⁰³ Arnold Joseph Toynbee, Daisaku Ikeda (1982). *The Toynbee-Ikeda Dialogue: Man Himself Must Choose*, pp. 45-46, and p. 80.

¹⁰⁴ Fu'ād Muḥammad Shibil (1968). *Toynbee's Historical Approach* (Manhaj Toynbee al-Tārīkhī), pp. 41-43.

Who is the one who takes the initiative in the face of adversity? Arnold Toynbee regards creative individuals, inspirational leaders, and a group with a vision and perception that provides a picture of the future and the mobility to face the challenges as dependents in the confrontation process; they are their dependents in the confrontation process. The majority of people would aid these cultures in overcoming their issues if they were persuaded to share in their anguish and suffering, or to duplicate and make things look to be the same as they are.¹⁰⁵

The three factors for the downfall of civilizations:

Assume that the existence of creative leaders occurred, and that certain societies began around an idea, such as the divine call to Islam, led by a prophet and moved by some creative people who advanced to its broad horizons. How does erosion and then decline occur? Toynbee outlines aspects of the collapse of civilization at three points, namely: the dimmest creative energy, the withdrawal of the majority loyalty and support for the dominant minority of the ruling, and the loss of the internal community.¹⁰⁶ As highlighted in Toynbee's three factors for the breakdown of civilizations, his rejection of the idea that civilizations fall for reasons external to them, such as exposure to an external invasion, and his rejection of the idea that societies resemble living organisms that go through the stages of childhood and adulthood, then old age and death, are both important points to consider.¹⁰⁷

The explanation for this is that if the creative few that were leading were weakened, their creativity would be lost, and they would automatically transform, while in power, into an arbitrary force. This arbitrary force prevents other innovators from presenting their innovations in order to protect their status, interest, and reputation, and it also prevents new thoughts and ideas from being supported by past accomplishments. The majority usually does not join the creative minority, and it either remains in confusion between the two parties or remains attached to the old. The consequence of this struggle leads to schism and the loss of the

¹⁰⁵ Toynbee, Arnold J (1947). *A Study of History* vol. 1, p. 86; Manal Khūrī (1960). *The Civilizational History of Toynbee* (al-Tārīkh al-Ḥaḍārī 'ind Toynbee), pp. 44-45; Karim Jabr Ḥasan (1993). *The Process of Civilizational Advancement* ('Amaliyat al-Nuhūd al-Ḥaḍārī) Beirut: Dār al-Hādī, p. 94 and p. 97.

¹⁰⁶ Eric Walter Frederick Tomlin ed. (1979). *Arnold Toynbee, A Selection from His Works* Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 47-48; Robert Angus Buchanan (1979). *History and Industrial Civilization* London: Macmillan International Higher Education, pp. 30-32.

¹⁰⁷ Toynbee, Arnold J (1947). *A Study of History*, vol. 1, p. 95 and p. 106; 'Imād al-Dīn Khalīl (1975). *Islamic Interpretation of History* (al-Tafsīr al-Islāmī li-Tārīkh) Beirut: Dar al-'Ilm li-Malāyīn, pp. 40-42; Karim Jabr Ḥasan (1993). *The Process of Civilizational Advancement* ('Amaliyat al-Nuhūd al-Ḥaḍārī), p. 172.

unity of the entity of society, and the beginning of a period that Arnold Toynbee calls "the time of turmoil", which leads to collapse.¹⁰⁸

Toynbee came to the conclusion that the creative minority had a significant effect on society as well as the extent to which the majority would follow it. Then, when they have gained access to the advancements that take place in the creative minority on the ground, they may comment on them. Apart from the fact that it uses abuse in front of other creators, which is regarded to be a fundamental component that forecasts the onset of a civil war, the most important factor is the decision made by the vast majority of people who support it (old or new creative). It is also difficult for even the most intelligent individuals to prevent a decline when a society is in the midst of a battle.¹⁰⁹

According to Sun Tzu, when it comes to preventing accidents, it is preferable to have numerous little avalanches rather than one massive avalanche in a particular circumstance.¹¹⁰

Second, the replies to Toynbee argue that there is a positive relationship between the level of obstacles and the level of responses.¹¹¹ That is, as the difficulties get more complex, so do the responses, until they reach the owners of the so-called golden medium.¹¹² This is achieved through a sequence of successful, semi-successful, and failed reactions to the obstacles that the Renaissance and civilization face. Until the nation is directed to resilience, the optimal solution or a mix of both, takes it to renaissance and civilization securely.¹¹³ The "golden technique" is the medium that propels the project forward significantly.¹¹⁴

¹⁰⁸ Arnold Toynbee (2020). *War and Civilization* (al-Ḥarb wa-l-Madaniyyah), tr. Aḥmad Suleiman Cairo: Wikālat al-Ṣaḥāfah al-ʿArabiyya, pp. 18-19; Raʿfat al-Sheikh (2000). *Tafsīr Masār al-Tārīkh* (Interpretation of the Course of History), pp. 197-199.

¹⁰⁹ Raʿfat Ghanimi Sheikh (2010). *Studies in the Civilization of the Islamic Nation* (Dirāsāt fā Ḥaḍarat al-ʿUmma al-Islāmiyya) Cairo: ʿAyn lil-Dirāsāt lil-Buḥūth wa-l-Dirāsāt al-Ijtīmāʿiyya, pp. 34-36; ʿImād al-Dīn Khalīl (1975). *Islamic Interpretation of History* (al-Tafsīr al-Islāmī li-Tārīkh), p. 40.

¹¹⁰ Bevin Alexander (2011). *Sun Tzu at Gettysburg: Ancient Military Wisdom in the Modern World* W. W. Norton & Company, p. 90.

¹¹¹ Arnold Toynbee (2020). *War and Civilization* (al-Ḥarb wa-l-Madaniyyah), tr. Aḥmad Suleiman, pp. 18-19.

¹¹² Patrice Gardiner (1959). *Theories of History* Oxford: Oxford University Press, p. 204; Raʿfat al-Sheikh (2000). *Tafsīr Masār al-Tārīkh* (Interpretation of the Course of History), p. 192; Mushḥī Zaid al-Tamāmī (2010). *Averroism Philosophy of History* (Falsafat al-Tārīkh ʿin Ibn Rushd) Damascus: Dar Ṣafaḥāt, p. 87, and p. 93.

¹¹³ Muḥammad Dhaifallah Baṭāinih (2002). *Islamic Civilization* (al-Ḥaḍārah al-Islāmiyyah) Amman: Dar Al-Furqān, 2002, pp. 21-22; Khaṭīb, Suleiman (1993). *The Philosophy of Civilization for Mālik ibn Nabī: An Islamic Study in the Light of Contemporary Reality* (Falsafat al-Ḥaḍārah ʿind Mālik Ibn Nabī), volume 4, Silsilat al-Rasāʾil al-Jāmiʿiyyah, Beirut: al-Muʿassasah al-Jāmiʿiyyah lil-Dirāsāt, pp. 66-67; Muḥammad Murād (1996). *The Great Historical Schools: Theoretical Studies in Research Methods and the Philosophy of History* (al-Madāris al-Tārīkhīyya al-Kubrā: Dirāsāt Naẓariyya fi Manāhij al-Baḥth wa Falsafat al-Tārīkh) Beirut: Maktabat al-Faqīh, pp. 286-287.

¹¹⁴ Raʿfat al-Sheikh (2000). *Tafsīr Masār al-Tārīkh* (Interpretation of the Course of History), p. 192; Batūl Aḥmad Jundiya (2011). *On the Thresholds of Civilization: Study of the Methods, Factors of Creation and Collapse* (ʿAlā ʿAtbāt al-Ḥaḍārah: Baḥth fi al-Sunana wa-ʿAwāmi al-Takhalaq wa-l-Inhiyār): *On the Thresholds of Civilization Volume 1 of Letters in the Philosophy of Civilization* Damascus: Dar al-Multaqā, p. 47.

This route of civilization's ascension rather than its rise and fall. It is observed that the curve of countries' development towards civilization does not follow a straight line or a constant curve. However, it travels through fluctuation variables and receptive curves, which clearly reflect the succession of negative attempts that the nation or civilization went through on its route to the top, until the golden means (the proper response) arrives and restores the curve to the upside. Thus, negative attempts and golden means are repeated until civilization reaches its pinnacle.

The influential doctrine is often one of these golden means of grandeur and influence, representing a vital and eternal adobe on which civilizations construct many of their subsequent methods and changes. This strategy is known as the influential doctrine, and it indicates a change that altered civilization and persisted with it, becoming one of the toughest constants to remove.¹¹⁵ Here are two real-world examples that illustrate the point. In the first place, think about what King Henry did for the political system in the United Kingdom. Laws promulgated by Henry the Twelfth were crucial in establishing and governing England during that period. They were enforced rigorously across the board, with everyone in society being expected to obey them. Henry's paradigm, which standardized or created English culture, remained in continual demand despite the fact that weak rulers ruled the following seventy years.¹¹⁶

Two examples come to mind: what Napoleon Bonaparte did in France when the French Revolution arose, when he applied contemporary management systems and founded the constituent assembly in order to meet the problems that lay ahead of him.¹¹⁷ Despite the fact that his experience was brief, it was sufficient to bring about a number of irrevocable alterations. A large number of these systems are still in use.¹¹⁸

Types of response's classified into two types based on their outcomes: successful responses and unsuccessful responses.¹¹⁹ Each of these two categories has the following logical consequences: Failed response: It leads to backwardness, a state characterized by internal turmoil and confusion and exterior signs such as the nation's reliance on outsiders for food, drink, and stories, as well as its thoughts and organization. It is a condition of detachment from the other, and it has all of the ingredients of colonialism.¹²⁰

The successful response goes through several phases: reveille, then awakening, then revival, and then civilization. As for reveille, it is the first stage in the dispersion of the clouds of golden meanness. We will use it here to describe the first stage of the civilized revival, its positive symptoms, and the sense of self and identity. It is the first stage in the dispersion of the clouds of golden meanness. We will use it here to describe the first stage of the civilized revival, its positive symptoms, and the sense of self and identity. Among its positive symptoms are self-confidence and identity. Among its negative symptoms is the lack of full adulteration of its deductive forms, for which it may, in part, appear chaotic and uncontrolled.¹²¹

The reveille is the harbinger of a new situation in a society, sometimes clear and sometimes confused, but it is the first cries of the foetus and the movement of someone who woke up from his sleep suddenly, but he has not yet properly woken up to his outer

¹¹⁵ Henry Lloyd Mason (1958). *Toynbee's Approach to World Politics: In His A Study of History* New Orleans: Tulane University, pp. 13-15.

¹¹⁶ Cort MacLean Johns (2021). *Industrial Revolutions: From Ctesibus to Mars* Benelux: Pumbo, pp. 388-389.

¹¹⁷ William Hazlitt (1895). *The Life of Napoleon Bonaparte*, Napoleon Society, Volume 3, pp. 87-88.

¹¹⁸ Walter Scott (1827). *The Life of Napoleon Bonaparte*, Paris: A. And W. Galignani, vol. 6, p. 175; Mohamed Tahir El-Misawi (2008). "Religion, Society, and Culture in Malik Bennabi's Thought," in Ibrahim Abu-Rabi (2008). *The Blackwell Companion to Contemporary Islamic Thought* Malden: John Wiley & Sons, pp. 228-229; Alban G. Widgery (2016). *Interpretations of History: From Confucius to Toynbee* New York: Routledge, pp. 249-250; Graeme Snooks (2002). *The Laws of History*, p. 77.

¹¹⁹ Stephen K. Sanderson (1995). *Civilizations and World Systems: Studying World-Historical Change* Lanham: Rowman Altamira, pp. 15-16.

¹²⁰ Henry Lloyd Mason (1958). *Toynbee's Approach to World Politics: In His A Study of History*, pp. 35-37.

¹²¹ Graeme Snooks (2002). *The Laws of History*, p. 77-78.

surroundings, so he may hit a seat without intending to. However, these threats heighten the waking and mobility of a complete awakening.¹²²

As for awakening, when a person wakes up, the mental curtain is gone and he or she realizes where they are in relation to everything and everyone else in the world. To navigate between the realms of material items and the human world, they have had to alter their locomotion. Positive signs include maturity, self-awareness, and deliberate, methodical behaviour.

Renaissance is the next state that organizes the world of ideas, and by it, it is meant the perceptions and realizations of the external world, as well as a set of principles, right and wrong, as well as feelings and sensations. The world of emotions awakens the individuals of some scholars as a single scholar and did not include him in the realm of ideas. Freed from the shackles of fear, a man rushes into it to play his role in all areas. Its positive symptoms, a sense of the thrill of work, discovery, and power, are a state that permeates all forms of life and gives time the value of the life of the nation, and it is granted to excellence and creativity as well.

Finally, civilization comes, which is a state of building the desired model in the real world, represented by a focalized intellectual model, and an advanced world of relationships and behavior, and that refers to social and civil life and the organized relationships of individuals and groups. The world of things refers to tangible physical structures such as factories, houses, bridges, and so on.

But, on the route to renaissance and civilisation, does each civilization have to pass through a period of chaos and randomness? As a result, any awakening occurs within a country of countries whose operational forms are semi-chaotic or random in many ways. As a result, every country that wishes to produce ideas capable of reaching the golden mean merely need a wide vision and the willingness to address issues. Continuing to use inefficient ways indicates turning around the self, but using new methods would result in a renaissance for the nation-state. This resentment necessitates the courage to investigate and profit from new possibilities rather than being pleased with already established solutions. The attainment of renaissance and civilizational leadership is not just an Islamic goal, but also a humanitarian need for the world.

¹²² Bassam Tibi (2014). *Political Islam, World Politics and Europe: From Jihadist to Institutional Islamism* London and New York: Routledge, pp. 3-4.

Conclusion

Since the Islamic country was able to overcome many obstacles, it is apparent that it was able to stand up against individuals with a strong will at various points in history. The golden means must not be forgotten in difficult times, but rather, the country must put its thoughts into action, and any unsuccessful efforts do not indicate that a solution does not exist. There's a chance it will find its right fit. Those looking for new experiences should use caution and alertness while dealing with others, particularly those who have opposing viewpoints. Prophetic tradition holds that "A believer is not stung by the same burrow more than once". People should not have to go through the same crises repeatedly, and this can only happen if they learn from their own mistakes and work to improve their strategies and tactics. Such an act is more urgent now and in the future.

There are warning bells ringing that if we don't address these issues, we'll simply be reinforcing our sense of backwardness, which is only real if we measure ourselves against others who have come before us and are farther along. Although colonialism has existed in various guises since the eleventh century and continues to this day in various forms, its true dominance only emerged after the Industrial Revolution and its enormous effects on European life, as well as what it left in terms of movement, communication, and destructive power, which upset the balance in favour of the West in some way.

In the face of such a direct confrontation, the Islamic community has already started to show its symptoms all over the place. It may fail, it may be reluctant, and the birth may be painful, but the people don't regard it as a victim of the unhappy time, as a fantasy, but rather with genuine investigation and deliberation. Its overall features must be embodied on the ground, after the first building blocks were laid at the beginning of this century, and intellectual, kinetic, and social forms have crystallized in our societies. Maturity resistance may be seen in the many stages of the post-construction phase. The awakening that is now taking place in this arena is a precursor to the Renaissance that will hopefully soon assemble its acts and embark on the grounds of the Renaissance. Afterwards, a worldwide society will have emerged.

Ibn Khaldūn and Toynbee offer us a new space of imagination, talking about challenges and their role in provoking the energies of societies. It introduces us to the Creative Human Theory and the Struggle with the Dominant Group. And the role of the general masses in advancing once again to new areas. In addition, what happened to the creative minority, or the group that was once creative but turned into an arbitrary force, and what that did to the renaissance.

Toynbee provides us with a picture of the leadership's behavior after the depletion of its creative constituency, so that its basis for speaking with the violators is law and discipline, and what is included in the literature, which does not speak about the project, but rather talks about legitimacy (entitlement to leadership). There is a big difference between interest in the project and its development and talk about legality. The project is a living thing that needs new tools and keeps growing, while legitimacy was built up in the past.

These phenomena help us to explain the fact that we live at different levels of our conditions, and they provide us with another introduction, wider than the *Muqadimma* of Ibn

Khaldūn. Nonetheless, it is not a contradiction to him, but rather a complement to what he discussed in his view of state rise and fall. It speaks of the whole league (*al-aṣabiya*) bond, the unified idea of individuals, and the importance of the continuation of the phenomenon of rebellion, the phenomenon of aggression, adding to it the phenomenon of roughness and strength to continue the process of pushing forward the growth of the state. When these two issues recede to the group that led the conflict and won, the process of the state's decline to the abyss of its downfall begins. The two theories are complementary in a way, and provide us with multiple explanations for the phenomena that we see around us today.¹²³

Toynbee and globalism imply that Toynbee was a major influence on the global theory of events and that no state was considered independent of others in being affected by the event or its action. The world has been divided into spots according to civilizations. Toynbee stresses that civilization is a wholly interconnected entity. These parts are socially coherent, symmetrical, and harmonious in all their elements, as they are real entities that stand alone, which implies the logic that changes in a part of civilization mean a change in the whole.

¹²³ Wajih Kawtharānī (2013). *Tārikh al-Ta'rikh: Itijāhāt, Madāris, Manāhij* (History of Historiography, Trends, Schools, Approaches), Beirut: al-Markaz al-'Arabī lil-Abḥāth, pp. 390-391.